

IMAGINARIES OF THE PRIMITIVE HUT IN BRAZILIAN MODERNISM

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RESUMO. Em um artigo publicado em 2009 na revista POS, explorei as múltiplas definições da noção de tectônica em arquitetura, destacando a contribuição das teorias de Gottfried Semper e Kenneth Frampton para a construção de discursos sobre a cultura construtiva. O arquétipo da cabana primitiva aparece simultaneamente como fundamento antropológico das origens da ornamentação, das técnicas construtivas e do simbolismo arquitetônico, e como uma tradição duradoura que permeia a história da arquitetura. À luz de uma leitura cruzada de debates históricos e contemporâneos, esta comunicação examina ocorrências raras, porém significativas, do imaginário da cabana primitiva e de técnicas construtivas ancestrais no modernismo brasileiro. Analisamos dois projetos emblemáticos: o pavilhão de Oscar Niemeyer no Parque do Ibirapuera (São Paulo, 1951), no qual a forma da oca se insinua em uma linguagem modernista — associação reforçada pela recepção pública da obra — e o conjunto habitacional de Acácio Gil Borsoi em Cajueiro Seco (Recife, 1963), que emprega a técnica da taipa em um sistema de pré-fabricação voltado à habitação social. Esses exemplos ilustram como o imaginário das arquiteturas vernaculares alimentou a reflexão e a prática modernistas, permeando tanto o imaginário coletivo quanto a concepção arquitetônica. Ao mobilizar esses dois casos, argumentamos que a cabana primitiva operou como figura crítica no modernismo brasileiro, renovando a compreensão das relações entre modernidade, tradição e identidade cultural, e abrindo novas perspectivas sobre a cultura construtiva da arquitetura moderna no Brasil.

1. REFRAMING FOUNDATIONAL MYTHS IN THE TROPICS

Considering the myth of the “primitive hut” as a critical instrument for discussing architectural theories and doctrines, Joseph Rykwert¹ argues that the concept developed throughout architectural history not as an anthropological fact but as a conceptual artefact. It has often been mobilized to justify the origins of architecture, theories of form and symbolism, and notions of nature and materiality. Charged with religious and anthropological dimensions, the myth permeates classicism, the Renaissance, and modernity because of its capacity to sustain ideas of innocence and universality and to evoke architecture as a primordial act. While Rykwert shows how European architects from Vitruvius to John Ruskin mobilized the primitive hut through architectural discourse, Gottfried Semper was the first to identify an actual anthropological artefact as a source model: the Caribbean hut exhibited at the London Universal Exhibition of 1851. Through his theory of the four elements of architecture, published that same year, Semper grounded architectural theory in one particular primitive hut, effectively displacing the discourse to the tropics by choosing an artefact from outside Europe as the primordial model of the complex act of building². This geographical displacement makes it especially pertinent to reconsider the myth of the primitive hut in the context of Brazilian modern architecture, as a way to reframe colonial narratives and to identify new critical instruments for discussing modernity in the tropics.

Seminal texts such as Oswald de Andrade’s *Manifesto Pau-Brasil* (1924) and *Manifesto Antropófago* (1928) laid the intellectual groundwork for a distinctly local modernism, advancing an anticolonial ethos grounded in the reappropriation of cultural references. Foundational writings on architecture and society—most notably Gilberto Freyre’s *Casa-Grande e Senzala* and *Sobrados e Mocambos*—constructed a mythology of Brazilian architectural history that is at once romanticized, enticing, nationalist, and highly exportable, while remaining deeply attentive to everyday life and culture. Freyre’s notion of Brazilian mixture foregrounds reciprocity among three cultures rather than the dominance of one over another, framing hybridity as cultural miscegenation. Whereas European modernism often linked the machine to a new artistic and architectural language, Brazilian modernists celebrated the interplay between art and the jungle and the creative reappropriation of vernacular traditions.³

Both internally and internationally, historiographic narratives promoted a cohesive vision of modern architecture in Brazil. As Nelci Tinem demonstrates, between 1930 and 1960 historians and critics concentrated on a limited set of currents and protagonists, contributing to a uniform narrative. Modern principles of functionality and new construction techniques were paired with an idea of modernity rooted in local traditions, yet without rigid attachment to them⁴. Within this framework, the work of architects such as Niemeyer, Costa, Artigas, and Reidy, and the opposition between Carioca and Paulista schools, dominates the discourse. Meanwhile, other productions outside Rio, São Paulo, and Brasília are relegated to a secondary position and excluded from the main narrative. A new reading of Tinem’s work also reveals how bioclimatic principles such as natural ventilation, shading, and local construction techniques were integrated as foundational elements of modern architecture, and in consequence largely detached from any idealized image of a primitive hut.

2. PRIMITIVE HUT, MATERIAL ORIGINS AND THE TECTONIC IMAGINATION

Nineteenth-century architectural culture was dominated by an interest in building construction, considered the very essence of architecture. The renewed gaze directed at Gothic architecture, especially in the context of historical revivals, was accompanied by a debate around the notion of style and constructive legibility. Within this debate Gottfried Semper, with his monumental *Der Stil*⁵, develops a genuine theory of style, implying a complete redefinition of the understanding of architecture. This redefinition passes through a reconsideration of architectural origins and a new approach to the architecture of his own time. The book is an examination of the material, technical and ideal preconceptions of style. Semper especially advocates an architecture coherent with the use of materials and ornaments, announcing an ideal relationship between material and form which would be a direct cause-and-effect relation justified by the technical origins of ornament⁶.

According to Semper, the traces left by primitive peoples and by the first civilizations indicate the influence of these first technical arts in the constitution of an aesthetic vocabulary under the form of a set of ornamental motifs which acquired a symbolic value and influenced the history of architecture. Based on their physical properties, he identifies four categories of raw material: pliable like fabric, soft and malleable like clay, in long and elastic forms like wood, or strong and dense like stone. Each primitive material is considered the ideal support of a technique.

In his attempt to explain the origin of architecture Semper oscillates between two arguments. The first concerns textile as an original gesture of protecting the body and of the first shelters, while the knot would be the first artistic symbol. The second refers to the myth of the primitive hut, which he revisits from his theory of the four elements of architecture. Rejecting the Vitruvian hypothesis that the Greek temple was derived from a primitive wooden version, Semper at the same time dismissed any relation between primitive human settlements and architectural motifs. As I have shown, the originality of Semper's theory is that the four primitive elements have no forms attributed a priori but are associated with raw materials and fabrication techniques.

As Mallgrave, notes, the hut in Semper has two aspects, a first as an 'ethnological fact' still recognizable in vernacular architecture, and a second as an 'ornamental analogue' highlighting a kind of human instinct to create ornaments and monumental forms. Moreover, they are not all necessarily present at the same time, or some elements may predominate over others. Through its analytical character, this theory identifies that architecture has an intrinsic material complexity manifested since the earliest times⁷.

Rather than contributing to discourse on the primitive hut, Kenneth Frampton develops a reflection on the constructive dimension and a critique of postmodernism. Through a series of publications culminating in the imposing book *Studies in Tectonic Culture*, he mobilizes both the notions of critical regionalism and tectonics⁸. For Frampton, the architectural object may appear in two modes of representation: (1) an ontological dimension corresponding to a 'structural-technical' object, that is, the one arising from the meeting of a technical need and whose forms reflect both the statics and the cultural status of the work; and (2) a representational dimension corresponding to the 'structural-symbolic' level of the object, involving a level of representation and symbolism. Frampton then identifies three conditions: the 'technical object' (which appears in the structural-technical mode),

the 'scenographic object' (which appears in the structural-symbolic mode) and the 'tectonic object,' which appears in both modes simultaneously.

Roberto Segre revisits the theories of the primitive hut, as well as the architectural frameworks developed by Semper and Frampton, drawing numerous global parallels with Latin-American vernacular and modern architecture. He observes that, in hot-humid climates, shade supplants the Semperian hearth as the central element of architecture. He further notes that neocolonial architecture functioned as an early site of experimentation preceding modern architecture, while climate adaptation and local cultural references later became integral to canonical modern production in Brazil.⁹

Taken together, Semper's theory of the four elements and Frampton's tectonic culture offer complementary ways of understanding architecture as a material, technical and symbolic practice. Semper situates the origins of building in textile and the primitive hut, emphasizing how materials and techniques generate form and meaning. Frampton reactivates this constructive ethos to critique postmodern image-making, and to reconsider architecture as simultaneously technical and symbolic. Together they supply a lens for examining buildings where constructive expression and symbolic reference coexist.

3. OSCAR NIEMEYER'S OCA: BETWEEN MODERNISM AND THE IMAGINARY OF INDIGENOUS HABITATION

Oscar Niemeyer's production in the 1950s signals a decisive shift in his architectural language. Whereas his earlier works were marked by what Kenneth Frampton calls the "intimate lyricism of his initial maturity," the 1950s ushered into a phase of "dynamic minimalism"¹⁰. As Philippou summarizes, Niemeyer's architecture conjugated architectural, structural, and topographical events "to achieve maximum fluidity," prioritizing "the sensual reality of the architectural experience." Moreover, "spectacle and luxury, pleasure, beauty and sensuality were emphatically affirmed as legitimate pursuits in Niemeyer's personal architectural manifesto"¹¹. These values became inseparable from his technical explorations in reinforced concrete, stressing his affinity with the expressive freedom of the Brazilian baroque, seen as precedent for a liberated architectural form.

The building known today as the Oca was originally called the Pavilhão das Artes (Pavilhão Lucas Nogueira Garcez), part of the Parque do Ibirapuera complex in São Paulo (1951). Papadaki described it in objective terms a dome directly resting on the ground, in contrast to the lightness of the neighboring auditorium, also by Niemeyer¹². Papadaki emphasizes the juxtaposition of these two masses and provides a technical and spatial description supported by photographs of the building under construction. Similarly, Josep Botey describes the pavilion primarily through its physical characteristics and dimensions: a dome only nine centimeters thick, resting on a circular ring with thirty circular openings¹³.

The term "oca" designates the large communal dwellings of several Indigenous groups in Brazil, particularly in the central plateaus and the Amazon region. The spontaneous association between the pavilion's domed form and an Indigenous archetype was so powerful that it eventually became institutionalized, replacing the original

official name. It exemplifies how public perception can inscribe vernacular references into the identity of modern buildings, producing unexpected layers of meaning.

This association becomes even more significant when read alongside Paulo Tavares's essay from 2013, which examines the urban development and territorial occupation of Brazil's central plateaus and the Amazon region¹⁴. This essay emphasizes that architects, planners, and geographers involved in governmental programs met with Indigenous groups. State-led programs of territorial occupation, initiated in the late 1930s and intensified in subsequent decades, both segregated and excluded Indigenous communities while simultaneously inscribing their culture into the national-modern imaginary. This paradoxical process combined cultural assimilation with anthropological documentation, revealing an explicit interest from architects in traditional Indigenous habitation. The magazine *Habitat* (founded by Lina Bo Bardi) featured several articles documenting Indigenous culture and architecture, introducing the figure of the "Folk Architect". Tavares concludes that the territorial "lines of conflict" in Brazil were also "channels for cultural exchange," pointing toward a decolonization of the state apparatus and contesting the foundational grounds of modernity.

The Oca can be read within this tension: while designed as part of a celebratory modernist park, it became a site where the image of Indigenous architecture infiltrated the modernist imaginary through popular naming and perception.

Niemeyer's design method starts with site considerations, program, and economic and material constraints, then is refined through sketches at a scale of 1:500 before discussing structural systems with technical experts¹⁵. This procedure reflects a clear hierarchy in which materiality plays a secondary role, subordinated to the expression of the whole — a stance markedly different from Semper ad Frampton's tectonic framework.

Nevertheless, Semper's theorization of the primitive hut — based on the Caribbean Hut he observed at the London Universal Exhibition of 1851 — had already displaced the myth geographically to the tropics. Semper implicitly introduced a non-European reference into architectural theory. In this sense, the Oca at Ibirapuera can be seen as an unintentional echo of Semper's displacement: a modern pavilion whose form evokes an Indigenous dwelling, inserted into the narrative of a modernizing Brazil. In doing so, it exemplifies how the myth of the primitive hut has been reinterpreted and re-signified in the tropics, not through deliberate design intention but through the interplay between form, public reception, and the broader politics of modernization and territorial occupation in Brazil.

4. CAJUEIRO SECO: ACÁCIO GIL BORSOI' SOCIAL HOUSING EXPERIMENT AND VERNACULAR ARCHITECTURE

Acácio Gil Borsoi stands as one of the most important figures of modern architecture in Northeast Brazil. His prolific body of work spans collective and individual housing, institutional buildings, and heritage preservation¹⁶. While his reputation within historiography often centers on his engagement with social housing, Borsoi's production also reflects a broader attempt to reconcile modernist ideals with local traditions and material

practices. Among his most emblematic initiatives, the Cajueiro Seco project illustrates his distinctive approach to the architectural and social challenges of mid-twentieth-century Pernambuco. The following discussion draws on material first developed in Marques and Amaral¹⁷, which is here reexamined to situate the Cajueiro Seco project within the broader theoretical framework. It is complemented by a reading of the extensive research done by Inglês de Souza¹⁸.

The historical context of Cajueiro Seco is inseparable from Pernambuco's turbulent housing policies. Created in 1940, the Serviço Social Contra o Mocambo (SSCM, Social Service Against Shanties) initially adopted a combative and repressive stance toward precarious settlements, mirroring the violent eradication of favelas in Rio de Janeiro. Yet, under the influence of politically and progressive professionals involved in public administration, this authoritarian apparatus paradoxically became a laboratory for pioneering social-housing experiments. By the 1960s, amid Brazil's general climate of reformist demands, Pernambuco's local contradictions between countryside and city were sharpened by the activism of peasants' alliances. This ferment, combined with the progressive municipal administration of Miguel Arraes as mayor of Recife (1960-1963), formed the backdrop for the Cajueiro Seco initiative. When he became Director of Construction at SSCM in 1963, Acacio Gil Borsoi encountered a heavily bureaucratic and paternalistic system, aimed mostly at supporting state-owned working-class housing areas. After noticing that these politics did little to nothing to empower communities, he decided to reconcile with ideas of social housing learnt early in his architectural education in Rio de Janeiro. At Jaboatão dos Guararapes, 800 families occupied and built precarious homes on a site near the historical location of the 1654 battle expelling Dutch forces from Pernambuco. In response, Borsoi, together with SSCM director Gildo Guerra, proposed the relocation of the houses, and the creation of a self-help community combining housing, cooperatives, schools, and productive facilities to foster social transformation. The project assembled politicians, social workers, educators such as Borsoi himself, and architecture students. The resettled population moved to a planned site near the original occupation. There, state agencies provided infrastructure while housing was constructed with improved but familiar techniques. Planning was decided directly with residents, who were taught the importance of spacing their homes.¹⁹

Drawing on the widespread Brazilian familiarity with taipa — wattle-and-daub construction — Borsoi introduced a rationalized version: an "industrial line" produced prefabricated wooden panels on site, alongside standardized doors, windows, and concrete sanitary units. A small local factory fabricated roofing materials from bundles of leaves treated with waterproof paint. Residents purchased assembly kits and defined their own house plans and façades. Labor mobilized families to build with wood frames and cover with a clay infill. The architect's intention was to promote empowerment of the local communities; however, the experiment came to an end with the military coup d'état in 1964, leaving no material evidence of the buildings on the site.

As discussed by Gilberto Freyre in *Sobrados e Mocambos*²⁰, the 'mocambo' embodies the precarious and marginalized dwelling of the urban poor; within this framework, such housing was not perceived as an ideal to emulate but as a condition related to the change of colonial politics, shifting from an agricultural setting to

urbanized conditions. In this context, Cajueiro Seco should not be read as a romantic or nostalgic revival of a “mocambo”.

In Semperian terms, Borsoi’s method drew on the “ethnological fact” of vernacular construction and transformed it into an industrialized version. From Frampton’s perspective, Cajueiro Seco can be understood as a “technical object”: an architecture in which constructive logic and social purpose coincide. As Cajueiro Seco represents an attempt to integrate local building knowledge and participatory process, it reveals how the idea of a primitive informed a socially engaged modernism in Brazil. Instead of representing an item to be eradicated or idealized, the mocambo represented collective agency.

5. INTERSECTING SYMBOLIC AND TECHNICAL IMAGINARIES

As argued above, the primitive hut functions simultaneously as a symbolic and an operative category within Brazilian modernism, shaping debates on materiality, technique, public reception, and social engagement. Niemeyer’s Oca and Borsoi’s Cajueiro Seco reveal two markedly different appropriations of this archetype. Whereas Niemeyer abstracts and monumentalizes the architectural space — privileging expressive form and sensory experience — its resonance remains primarily within the public imaginary. Borsoi, by contrast, materializes the archetype through the reinterpretation of vernacular construction, and social engagement.

In the Oca, the homogeneous concrete shell and spatial fluidity exemplify a formalist, anti-tectonic approach. In Cajueiro Seco, the tactile materiality of earth and wood, coupled with prefabrication and self-help labor, affirms a Semperian attention to material and technique. These distinctions underscore the dual capacity of the primitive hut: as a symbolic referent (whether intended or ascribed) and as a practical model informing the rationalization of vernacular methods and collective construction. If Niemeyer’s pavilion and design ethos appear to correspond to Frampton’s ontological dimension of architecture, public reception situates the Oca primarily within a symbolic register. Borsoi’s Cajueiro Seco resists such clear categorization: its structural and technical dimension alone is insufficient to account for the project. Because its prefabricated methods reinterpret ethnological artefacts and living traditions, it intersects both the technical and symbolic imaginaries. Both projects reaffirm the relevance of the primitive hut as an analytical lens for Brazilian modernism and suggest its continued significance for contemporary architectural debates.

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